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Influence of different hydrocarbons on impurities and minority carrier lifetime in 4H-SiC epitaxial layers

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Abstract

This study explores the influence of different hydrocarbons, methane and propane, on the properties of 4H-SiC epitaxial layers grown by chloride-based chemical vapor deposition. By systematically varying the C/Si and N/C ratios during epitaxial growth, and employing a comprehensive suite of characterization techniques, a better understanding of how growth conditions influence material properties is gained. We show that the n-type dopant incorporation strongly depends on the choice of hydrocarbon especially at lower doping levels. Furthermore, we have observed that methane contributes to a relatively longer carrier lifetime value compared to propane, though a similar lifetime limiting carbon vacancy defect concentration has been observed for both hydrocarbons in as-grown epitaxial layers. Moreover, additional defect levels are also suggested by deep-level transient spectroscopy, potentially related to chlorine complexes, with varying concentrations depending on the choice of hydrocarbon and C/Si ratio. These observations offer insights into the complicated interplay of factors influencing doping, minority carrier lifetime, and defect formation in 4H-SiC epitaxial layers during the epitaxial growth process, and contribute to the optimization of growth parameters depending on the application in question.

1. Introduction

The established role of silicon carbide (SiC) in power electronics and its growing importance in quantum technology have fueled significant interest in epitaxial growth to achieve thick epitaxial layers with ultra-high purity and low intrinsic defect density. The use of such thick epitaxial layers for high-power devices requires controlled low doping in the drift layer to withstand high blocking voltages, and in particular high charge carrier lifetime to ensure lower forward losses during device operation. For quantum applications, ultra-high purity is crucial to enable single spin defects with long coherence time. Among several SiC polytypes, 4H-SiC stands out due to its superior properties, such as a wide bandgap, high thermal conductivity, and exceptional saturation drift velocity [1]. These attributes, alongside the commercial availability of 200 mm substrates, make it particularly appealing for both power electronics and quantum applications. However, the performance of SiC-based devices is critically dependent on the quality of the epitaxial layers, with both macroscopic and microscopic imperfections potentially being detrimental. Stacking faults, dislocations, micropipes, downfalls, and surface defects can all impact device performance and reliability. Furthermore, uncontrolled doping, impurity incorporation, and the formation of deep levels during epitaxial growth are major concerns. The latter can negatively affect minority carrier lifetime (MCL), an important characteristic of SiC epitaxial layers for ultra-high-power applications [1], and can also lead to decoherence and reduced qubit fidelity in quantum devices [2, 3]. Accordingly, the demand for ultra-high-quality, pure, and defect-free epitaxial layers has prompted extensive research efforts to address these challenges.

The chemical vapor deposition (CVD) process for growing 4H-SiC epitaxial layers employs two distinct approaches: standard chemistry and chloride-based (Cl-based) chemistry. While silane (SiH_4) typically serves as the silicon source in the standard process, the introduction of HCl alongside SiH_4 or the use of Cl-containing silicon precursors leads to a Cl-based process. Although these processes have been extensively explored and exhibit substantial differences [4–7], both can utilize various hydrocarbons as the carbon source. The choice of hydrocarbon, despite being less studied, is reported to critically influence the quality of the epitaxial layers [8, 9]. Propane (C_3H_8) is a well-studied and commonly used C precursor for the epitaxial growth of 4H-SiC through CVD, whereas very few studies have been reported on methane (CH_4) and ethylene (C_2H_4). We have recently shown that CH_4 and C_3H_8 can impact epitaxial growth dynamics through their distinct surface kinetics and gas phase species which leads to the formation of unique epitaxial defects and surface properties [8].

The present study undertakes a systematic comparison of the influence of different hydrocarbons, specifically CH_4 and C_3H_8 , in a Cl-based process, on doping incorporation, MCL, impurity introduction, and deep-level formation in 4H-SiC epitaxial layers. By analyzing the resulting defect structures and their impact on MCL, this study aims to develop a comprehensive understanding of the underlying mechanisms.

2. Experimental

The epitaxial layers investigated in this study were grown in a horizontal hot-wall CVD reactor equipped with gas foil rotation on $20 \times 20 \text{ mm}^2$, 4° off-axis 4H-SiC substrates cut from commercially available production-grade 150 mm n-type wafers. Trichlorosilane (TCS) was used as the silicon source, while either CH_4 or C_3H_8 served as the carbon source, with H_2 as the carrier gas. To intentionally dope the epitaxial layers, N_2 was introduced into the reactor during the epitaxial growth. All layers followed a similar process except for variations in the studied parameters. Each epitaxial layer was grown for 1 h at 1640°C at a growth rate of $25 \mu\text{m h}^{-1}$, corresponding to $25 \mu\text{m}$ thickness. Prior to the growth, all substrates underwent *in-situ* surface preparation under a heavy flow of the carrier gas for 5 min at the growth temperature. Two sets of samples were grown and are distinguished based on whether the N/C ratio (fixed C/Si ratio) or C/Si ratio (fixed N/C ratio) was varied. Both N/C and C/Si ratios are determined by using the flow rates introduced in the growth zone through mass flow controllers.

In the first set of samples (Set-I), the C/Si ratio was fixed at 1.2. Different epitaxial layers were then grown by varying the N/C ratio by changing the amount of introduced nitrogen and alternating between CH_4 and C_3H_8 as the carbon source. The second set of samples (Set-II) was grown with differing C/Si ratios, achieved by varying the amount of introduced carbon source while keeping a fixed TCS flow rate. The rest of the growth parameters were kept fixed. The C/Si ratios ranged from 0.9 to 1.3 in steps of 0.1, alternating between CH_4 and C_3H_8 as the carbon source. During the growth process of these layers, different amounts of nitrogen gas flow were introduced to maintain a fixed N/C ratio at each C/Si ratio. The details of the two Sets of samples are summarized in table 1.

Capacitance–voltage (CV) measurements were performed by a mercury probe station, to determine the doping type and concentration of the studied epitaxial layers. Time-resolved photoluminescence (TRPL) measurements were performed at room temperature to reveal the MCL in the samples by using a 355 nm excitation laser and collecting the near band edge (NBE) emitted light passed through a bandpass filter at 390 nm (FWHM: 10 nm) by a photomultiplier tube (PMT). Another bandpass filter at 530 nm (FWHM: 10 nm) was also used in TRPL measurements for qualitative comparison of boron-related deep-level defects [10]. Deep-level transient spectroscopy (DLTS) was conducted to investigate deep-level defects in as-grown epitaxial layers. The DLTS measurements were performed using a Boonton-7200 high-precision capacitance meter operating at a test frequency of 1 MHz in combination with an Agilent 81110A pulse generator. Measurements were taken at a reverse bias of -10 V and filling pulse voltages of 10 V , using time windows of 20–640 ms and a temperature range between 20 K–600 K. The DLTS spectra presented in this study have been slightly smoothed to remove noise and enable Arrhenius analysis to extract defect parameters (activation energy, E_A , and electron capture cross-section, σ_n).

3. Results

3.1. Influence of N/C ratio

Figure 1 illustrates the relationship between the introduced N/C ratio and the free carrier concentration for Set-I samples. It can be seen that as the N/C ratio increases, the doping concentration increases as well, however with different rates for each hydrocarbon. Different N/C ratios are divided into three regions R1, R2, and R3. At the lowest value of N/C ratio of 9.34×10^{-5} (region R1 in figure 1), the measured doping concentration for CH_4 is $1.4 \times 10^{13} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ which is an order of magnitude lower than for C_3H_8 , at

Table 1. Growth parameters for the Set-I and Set-II samples together with corresponding sample IDs.

Hydrocarbon	Sample ID (Set-I)	C/Si	N/C ($\times 10^{-4}$)	Sample ID (Set-II)	C/Si	N/C ($\times 10^{-4}$)
CH ₄	MD1	1.2	0.934	M1	0.9	2.56
	MD2		1.83	M2	1.0	
	MD3		3.66	M3	1.1	
	MD4		7.31	M4	1.2	
	MD5		14.6	M5	1.3	
C ₃ H ₈	PD1	1.2	0.934	P1	0.9	2.56
	PD2		2.56	P2	1.0	
	PD3		14.6	P3	1.1	
				P4	1.2	
				P5	1.3	

Figure 2. (a) TRPL spectra at different N/C ratios for the two hydrocarbons for the samples in Set-I. (b) Corresponding MCL at different free carrier concentrations extracted from decay curves in (a). The dashed lines represent fitted curves using the following empirical fit function: $\tau = \tau_0 / (1 + \frac{N}{N_0})$ [11], where τ is doping dependent MCL, τ_0 is maximum MCL achieved in lower doping concentrations, N is doping concentration and N_0 is a constant that characterizes the doping dependence.

$1.4 \times 10^{14} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. At intermediate N/C ratios (region R2 figure 1) this difference starts to become smaller but still slightly higher doping is observed for C₃H₈. At higher N/C ratios (region R3 figure 1), both curves eventually start to meet. Now, there is no difference in the doping concentration and both hydrocarbons show a similar increase in the doping concentration at around $1 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ with the increasing N/C ratio.

TRPL decay curves of the samples in set-I are shown in figure 2(a). MCL values extracted by exponential fitting on the linear part of the slow decay component of the curves shown in figure 2(a) are presented in

Table 2. Extracted MCLs from TRPL decay curves for the (left side) set-I samples at different N/C ratios corresponding to different free carrier concentrations ($N_D - N_A$) and (right side) set-II samples at different C/Si ratios together with their corresponding measured free carrier concentrations ($N_D - N_A$).

Sample ID (Set-I)	MCL (μ s)	$N_D - N_A$ (cm^{-3})	Sample ID (Set-II)	MCL (μ s)	$N_D - N_A$ (cm^{-3})
MD1	1.1	1.4×10^{13}	M1	0.53	2.6×10^{15}
MD2	0.95	1.9×10^{14}	M2	0.83	3.2×10^{14}
MD3	0.82	3.3×10^{14}	M3	0.80	5.1×10^{14}
MD4	0.94	5.3×10^{14}	M4	1.02	2.8×10^{14}
MD5	0.85	7.0×10^{14}	M5	0.86	1.7×10^{14}
			P1	0.04	2.7×10^{16}
PD1	0.52	1.4×10^{14}	P2	0.30	1.4×10^{15}
PD2	0.44	3.5×10^{14}	P3	0.53	9.8×10^{14}
PD3	0.23	6.5×10^{14}	P4	0.44	3.5×10^{14}
			P5	0.60	2.5×10^{14}

table 2. Using these values, the relationship between MCL and doping concentration in this set of samples (see figure 2(b)) shows that CH_4 as a carbon source leads to significantly longer MCL across all N/C ratios (i.e. all doping concentrations) as compared to C_3H_8 . The measured lifetime is almost double for the epitaxial layers grown with CH_4 ($\sim 1.1 \mu\text{s}$) compared to the epitaxial layers grown with C_3H_8 ($\sim 0.5 \mu\text{s}$). Additionally, for both hydrocarbons, increasing the N/C ratio and thus the doping concentration exhibits a similar trend of MCL reduction. Detailed extracted values for doping concentrations and MCL in this set of samples are presented in table 2 (left side).

3.2. Influence of C/Si ratio

Figure 3 shows the measured free carrier concentrations at different C/Si ratios for both hydrocarbons. As seen, increasing the C/Si ratio from 0.9 to 1.0 substantially decreases the free carrier concentration (from $2.6 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ to $3.2 \times 10^{14} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ for CH_4 and from $2.7 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ to $1.4 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ for C_3H_8), followed by a slight increase at a C/Si ratio of 1.1, and eventually reaching a plateau around low 10^{14} cm^{-3} at higher C/Si ratios. It is also clear that using CH_4 as the carbon source results in lower nitrogen doping incorporation than for the C_3H_8 case at all C/Si ratios. The difference between the measured values of n-type doping concentration for CH_4 and C_3H_8 decreases when moving from low C/Si ratios to higher ones.

TRPL decay curves for the two different carbon sources at different C/Si ratios are presented in figure 4(a). The relationship between the extracted MCLs from these curves and the C/Si ratio for the two hydrocarbons is plotted in figure 4(b). The measured MCL is higher for CH_4 samples compared to C_3H_8 at all C/Si ratios, and for both hydrocarbons, it tends to increase with increasing C/Si ratio. Furthermore, there appears to be a saturation limit of measured MCL for both hydrocarbons at around $1 \mu\text{s}$ for CH_4 and around $0.6 \mu\text{s}$ for C_3H_8 . Detailed extracted values for doping concentrations and MCL in this set of samples are presented in table 2 (right side).

Figure 4. (a) TRPL decay curves for the two carbon sources and at different C/Si ratios. (b) Corresponding MCL of the Set-II samples at different C/Si ratios. The dashed line represents an exponential fit to the data.

Figure 5. DLTS spectra of representative samples of Set-II for the two hydrocarbons: (a) CH_4 , (b) C_3H_8 , and (c) and (d) show a zoomed-in view of the temperature window of 350–550 K for CH_4 and C_3H_8 samples, respectively. The dashed line in (c) is a Gaussian fit to peak B for C/Si: 1.3.

3.3. Deep level incorporation

DLTS measurements were carried out on representative samples of each carbon source material to investigate the incorporation of deep-level defects. Figure 5 shows the DLTS spectra of the representative samples from Set-II. It can be seen that for the epitaxial layers grown with either CH_4 or C_3H_8 as the carbon source, the dominant peaks are the ones related to the carbon vacancy (V_C), namely the $Z_{1/2}$, a prominent MCL-limiting

defect in n-type 4H-SiC epitaxial layers [12, 13]), and $EH_{6/7}$ levels (see figures 5(a) and (b)). However, a closer look at the temperature window of 350–550 K reveals the presence of additional smaller peaks (indicating lower defect concentration than for $Z_{1/2}$) at around 400 K (labeled peak A) and 480 K (labeled peak B), as shown in figures 5(c) and (d). The epitaxial layers grown with C_3H_8 show substantially higher signal intensity for the A and B peaks as compared to the CH_4 samples (where only B peak is distinguishable for C/Si: 1.3), translating into higher concentration of these defect levels in C_3H_8 samples. Interestingly, in the case of CH_4 only the B peak is present and for C/Si: 1.3, where in the case of C_3H_8 , the A peak is stronger than the B peak for the C/Si ratio of 1.2, but for the C/Si ratio of 1.3, the B peak becomes more prominent.

The concentrations of the $Z_{1/2}$ centers extracted from DLTS spectra are plotted against the C/Si ratio for both sample series grown with CH_4 or C_3H_8 in figure 6. It can be seen that, for both hydrocarbons, the $Z_{1/2}$ concentration is comparatively high for a C/Si ratio of 0.9, or in other words, under carbon-deficient growth conditions. However, when moving toward C/Si ratios above 1.0, the $Z_{1/2}$ concentration drops significantly and is measured almost similar around $2 - 3 \times 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ for all samples. It is to be noted that at a lower C/Si ratio of 0.9, the epitaxial layer grown with CH_4 shows an order of magnitude lower concentration of $Z_{1/2}$ defects than the C_3H_8 one, even though both samples were grown under the same conditions and one after the other.

530 nm decay parameters extracted from TRPL measurements at 530 nm on representative samples from Set-II are shown in figure 7. We have previously shown that 530 nm decay constant is inversely proportional to shallow boron concentration and the area under the decay curve at this wavelength is proportional to the D-center concentration [10]. It can be seen in figure 7(a) that both of the hydrocarbons show similar decay constant, implying an equal concentration of shallow boron in all of them. However, from figure 7(b) it is seen that there is a significant difference between the area under the 530 nm decay for the samples grown with different hydrocarbons, with larger values extracted for C_3H_8 samples, suggesting a higher concentration of D-center for the samples grown with C_3H_8 as the carbon source.

4. Discussion

4.1. Nitrogen incorporation and n-type doping concentration

To explain the differences observed in the doping concentrations in the epitaxial layers grown with CH_4 and C_3H_8 in both sets of samples (figures 1 and 3), it is necessary to review the nitrogen incorporation mechanism during the epitaxial growth of 4H-SiC. Nitrogen occupies carbon sites in the 4H-SiC lattice during epitaxial growth. Although N_2 molecules ($N \equiv N$) are extremely stable, they can decompose in the presence of H_2 and CH_3 [14], forming HCN molecules. These HCN molecules are believed to be the primary contributors to nitrogen doping during SiC epitaxial growth [14], and there is expected to be no difference in their effect regardless of whether C_3H_8 or CH_4 is used as a carbon source. Therefore, nitrogen's gas-phase chemistry should be similar in both cases.

On the other hand, different hydrocarbons during the epitaxial growth decompose into different kinds of molecules in the gas phase. Moreover, the sticking coefficients of species derived from different hydrocarbons are reported to differ [15]. The initial decomposition of CH_4 results in methyl radicals (CH_3) and hydrogen (H) where CH_3 exhibits a sticking coefficient of 1×10^{-2} , whereas, C_3H_8 decomposes into ethyl radicals (C_2H_5) and CH_3 . The sticking coefficient for C_2H_5 is significantly higher at 3×10^{-2} , while CH_3 maintains

its value of 1×10^{-2} regardless of its origin. Accordingly, the different sticking coefficients of the species affect their mobilities on the surface and lead to distinct surface morphologies depending on the hydrocarbon used during the epitaxial growth [8].

In general, nitrogen incorporation into the 4H-SiC lattice is proportional to the amount of introduced N₂ molecules [16]. In figure 1 we observe an almost linear relationship between nitrogen flow rates and doping concentration for C₃H₈ in all regions. However, at very low doping levels ($< 2 \times 10^{14} \text{ cm}^{-3}$), corresponding to regions R1 and R2 in figure 1, the increase in doping concentration is not linear for CH₄. At low N/C ratios, and considering similar mass transport of N and C species, the actual incorporation is dependent on the surface diffusivity of carbon-containing species. Accordingly, less agile carbon-containing species in C₃H₈ compared to the CH₄ ones would lead to higher N incorporation and consequently higher doping concentrations in the epitaxial layers grown with C₃H₈.

At relatively higher doping levels ($> 2 \times 10^{14} \text{ cm}^{-3}$), corresponding to region R3 in figure 1, the increase in doping concentration becomes linear with the flow rate of N for CH₄ as well, and both curves merge in this region. It seems that at relatively higher doping levels corresponding to N/C ratio in region R3, the nitrogen incorporation efficiency is no longer controlled by the higher surface diffusivity of carbon-containing species derived by CH₄. Instead, it is controlled by mass transport similar to C₃H₈. Hence, for doping concentrations in this region, no difference in nitrogen incorporation efficiency is observed between CH₄ and C₃H₈.

As shown in figure 3, increasing the C/Si ratio leads to reduced nitrogen incorporation for both CH₄ and C₃H₈, as evidenced by lower doping concentrations. This agrees with the site-competition model [9, 17], where a relatively higher concentration of carbon-containing species at a high C/Si ratio is distributed evenly over the surface and suppresses nitrogen incorporation. However, the reduction rates differ between the two hydrocarbons. Here, the difference in the mobility of different carbon-containing species can also explain the observed variations in doping incorporation rates for different hydrocarbons.

While HCN is the main species for nitrogen incorporation (hence, similar mobility of N species in both cases), the different mobilities of carbon-containing species can result in varying nitrogen incorporation rates when considering the site-competition model for N incorporation [9, 17]. In other words, the higher surface diffusivity of carbon-containing species when CH₄ is used as a carbon source suppresses the efficient incorporation of nitrogen into the growing lattice by occupying more of the available sites compared to nitrogen species. Hence, a lower doping concentration is the result. On the other hand, the higher doping concentrations for samples grown using C₃H₈ can be explained by the lower relative diffusivity of carbon-containing species when C₃H₈ is used as a carbon source, compared to nitrogen species, and leads to a relatively higher doping concentration.

The local minima in the free carrier concentrations of both CH₄ and C₃H₈ samples (figure 3) at a C/Si ratio of 1.0 could be related to the gas-phase chemistry, as it is consistent across both hydrocarbons. This suggests optimized gas-phase conditions where the relatively (compared to the introduced amount of carbon source) maximum effective C/Si ratio can be achieved, hence suppressing nitrogen incorporation most effectively. This specific condition is also observed in figure 6, where the $Z_{1/2}$ concentration is lowest for the C/Si ratio of 1.0 and can be explained by perfect thermodynamic equilibrium conditions at this ratio.

4.2. MCL and deep levels

In a previous study, we reported a significantly higher MCL of about $2.5 \mu\text{s}$ in $25 \mu\text{m}$ thick epitaxial layers grown with CH_4 as a carbon source under optimized growth conditions [10]. The present study confirms our previous observation, however, the measured lifetime is relatively low (up to $1.1 \mu\text{s}$ in $25 \mu\text{m}$ thick epitaxial layers) as compared to previously reported values. This could be due to the history of the growth zone or non-optimized growth conditions for MCL. This study highlights the comparison of MCL in epitaxial layers grown through two different carbon precursors under the same growth conditions. Figure 4(b) clearly shows the advantage of using CH_4 over C_3H_8 to achieve longer MCLs over a wide range of C/Si ratios. The lowest measured MCLs at a C/Si ratio of 0.9 for both hydrocarbons can be attributed to the higher measured $Z_{1/2}$ concentration (see figure 6), as the formation of V_C -related defect levels is expected to be enhanced in a carbon-deficient growth regime [18, 19]. As the C/Si ratio increases, lower $Z_{1/2}$ concentrations are expected, leading to improved MCLs. We also observe an upper limit for MCL above a certain C/Si ratio for each hydrocarbon, where the MCL becomes saturated. However, the reason for lower MCL for C_3H_8 samples still needs to be addressed. Furthermore, as a result of higher doping concentrations, an increase in carrier recombination rates through direct band-to-band and Auger recombination is expected, leading to lower measured MCLs [20]. Accordingly, a small reduction in MCL at relatively higher doping levels ($>1 \times 10^{14} \text{ cm}^{-3}$), as observed in figure 2(b), can be attributed to the doping dependency of the MCL.

To understand the variations in MCLs for different hydrocarbons, a closer examination of the DLTS results is necessary. Figure 6 demonstrates that there is no major difference in $Z_{1/2}$ concentrations for both hydrocarbons for C/Si ratio in the range of 1–1.3. This suggests that, under these growth conditions, V_C formation is not affected by the C/Si ratio. On the contrary, a significantly higher concentration of $Z_{1/2}$ from both hydrocarbons at a C/Si ratio of 0.9, which induces a carbon-deficient growth regime, suggests a strong impact on V_C formation. Over an order of magnitude lower $Z_{1/2}$ concentration observed in epitaxial layer grown with CH_4 , compared to C_3H_8 , could also be attributed to high surface mobility of carbon-containing species derived from CH_4 , leading to more efficient filling of carbon lattice site and hence reduced carbon vacancies in the epitaxial layer. However, at a C/Si ratio of 1 and above, the surface mobility of carbon-containing species does not play any significant role and the $Z_{1/2}$ concentration becomes independent of it.

Although similar $Z_{1/2}$ concentrations are measured for both hydrocarbons at different C/Si ratios except for C/Si ratio 0.9, the DLTS spectra of C_3H_8 samples (figures 5(b) and (d)) show additional peaks labeled A (at ~ 400 K) and B (at ~ 480 K) to higher density than those found in CH_4 samples (figures 5(a) and (c)). To determine how the different measured MCLs are related to these defect levels and to the hydrocarbons, the origin of these defects has to be identified. Several studies have reported peaks in DLTS spectra of the 350–500 K temperature range for n-type 4H-SiC epitaxial layers (regardless to the standard or Cl-based chemistry of the growth process) with different labeling as summarized below.

A set of peaks named the ON-family of defect levels (including the ON1, ON2, ON0a and ON0b peaks) have been observed in 4H-SiC epitaxial layers after either thermal oxidation, carbon implantation or carbon injection by annealing with a carbon cap (i.e. a graphitized photoresist) [21–25].

Some or all of these defect levels have been suggested to have a carbon interstitial related nature, most likely in the form of clusters of C-atoms, as they are stable up to temperatures where single C interstitials would have disappeared [26]. These peaks appear in a similar temperature range as the peaks A and B observed herein (see figure 5), i.e. around 360 K for ON1 and 470 K for ON2. Note that ON2 typically appears as a broad peak containing at least two distinct defect levels [25], which is not the case for peak B. It should also be kept in mind that peak temperatures are listed here for reference, but are not directly comparable, as the peak position depends on, e.g. the rate window used during the DLTS measurement.

He^+ -implantation of 4H-SiC epitaxial layers, followed by an annealing step at 430°C , causes two peaks to appear that are named $\text{RD}_{1/2}$, at ~ 450 K, and RD_3 , at ~ 560 K [28].

Proton irradiation introduces a similar set of peaks labeled EH_4 and EH_5 , and located at ~ 400 K and ~ 500 K, respectively [29]. EH_4 has been assigned three individual contributions, and the set of defect levels contained in the EH_4 and EH_5 peaks have been tentatively attributed to the carbon antisite-vacancy pair [30].

Cl^+ -implantation of 4H-SiC epitaxial layers leads to the appearance of multiple peaks in the temperature range of 400 K to 500 K depending on the post-implantation annealing conditions. After annealing at 700°C for 15 min, a broad peak around 400 K labeled EH_4 appears, while two peaks that are named Ci_4 (at ~ 360 K) and Ci_5 (at ~ 480 K) form after an 1800°C annealing step [27].

In as-grown epitaxial layers, the type of deep-level defects observed in DLTS spectra depends on the growth chemistry. For instance, epitaxial layers grown through standard chemistry mainly show V_C -related $Z_{1/2}$ and $\text{EH}_{6/7}$ defect levels, while epitaxial layers grown through Cl-based chemistry have shown additional defect levels. These include the Fe1 and A(1) levels in the lower temperature (200–350 K) range, and the A(2)

Table 3. Parameters of the deep levels appearing in the same temperature range as the *A* and *B* peaks, as measured for Cl-implanted epitaxial layers of [27], as-grown samples of [5], and epitaxial layers grown in this study. The listed parameters include trap level (E_T), electron capture cross-section (σ_n), hole capture cross-section (σ_p), and net carrier concentration in the sample for reference.

Identification	E_T (eV)	σ_n (cm ²)	σ_p (cm ²)	net carrier concentration (cm ⁻³)	Source
<i>A</i>	0.85	1.15×10^{-15}		3.5×10^{14}	This study (as-grown, Cl-chemistry)
<i>B</i>	0.95	1.66×10^{-16}		3.5×10^{14}	This study (as-grown, Cl-chemistry)
A(2)	0.90	6.0×10^{-16}		$4 \times 10^{13} - 8 \times 10^{15}$	[5] (as-grown, Cl-chemistry)
RB1	1.05	2.0×10^{-16}	proposed $\approx (5 \pm 2) \times 10^{-15}$	$4 \times 10^{13} - 8 \times 10^{15}$	[5] (as-grown, Cl-chemistry)
Ci ₄	1.06	3×10^{-14}		$7 - 8 \times 10^{15}$	[27] (Cl ⁺ -implanted)
Ci ₅	1.3	2×10^{-13}		$7 - 8 \times 10^{15}$	[27] (Cl ⁺ -implanted)

and RB1 deep levels in the temperature region of relevance for identifying the *A* and *B* peaks, i.e. around 420 K and 520 K, respectively [5].

The ON1 and ON2 defect levels have been reported to influence MCL in both n- and p-type epitaxial layers, though more effectively in p-type layers [31]. Furthermore, the scope of their influence is not expected to be greater than that of the $Z_{1/2}$ center [31]. The ON1 and ON2 peaks are usually observed in epitaxial layers only after post-growth processes such as thermal oxidation, carbon implantation, or other thermal injection of carbon; hence, they cannot be the ones observed in figures 5(c) and (d). This is further emphasized by the fact that ON2 contains two distinct contributions, a fact that is not evident for the peak *B* from the DLTS measurements performed herein. Similarly, RD_{1/2}, RD₃, EH₄ and EH₅ are reported to be formed in epitaxial layers after implantation or irradiation and are not present in as-grown layers [28, 29]. It should also be noted that these defects are reported to almost disappear after annealing at around 1000 °C [28, 29], which is far below the growth temperature of the epitaxial layers studied herein. Thus, the peaks labeled as *A* and *B* in figure 5 are likely of different origin.

There are two peaks appearing in as-grown epitaxial layers grown with Cl-based chemistry that may be related to the *A* and *B* peaks, namely A(2) and RB1 [5]. Of these, the impact of A(2) on carrier lifetime is not clear. The RB1 defect level is suggested to be either an intrinsic defect similar to RD_{1/2} or EH₅, or a complex involving iron. Although the RB1 defect level is proposed to be related to iron complexes [5], it should be mentioned that the epitaxial layers showing RB1 defects in that study were grown with Cl-based chemistry as well (in the same reactor where the epitaxial layers of this study were grown). Furthermore, such defects are not observed in as-grown epitaxial layers intentionally doped with iron during epitaxial growth [32].

Finally, the Ci₄ and Ci₅ peaks are likely related to Cl, as they only appear after Cl⁺-implantation followed by annealing at 1800 °C, indicating a defect complex involving Cl. Ci₄ and Ci₅ were tentatively assigned to two different charge states of the Cl_CV_{Si} complex, having closely spaced energy levels at $E_C - 1.06$ eV and $E_C - 1.3$ eV, respectively, accompanied by similar and relatively large capture cross sections of 3×10^{-14} cm² and 2×10^{-13} cm² (E_C denotes the conduction band edge) [27]. Additionally, although Ci₄ and Ci₅ are formed as a result of Cl implantation, they were not detectable after low-temperature annealing in the range of 700 °C–1400 °C. The peaks were detected only when the epitaxial layers were annealed at 1800 °C [27], emphasizing the likelihood that they are related to a defect complex, such as the proposed Cl_CV_{Si} center. This tentative assignment is in part supported by a recent theoretical work that predicts the four defect levels of the Cl_CV_{Si}(0/−) acceptor transition, related to the different hexagonal (*h*) and pseudo-cubic (*k*) lattice sites in 4H-SiC yielding four distinct complexes, in the range of 1.1 eV–1.4 eV [33]. Thus, the Ci₄ and Ci₅ peaks could be related to the (0/−) transition of Cl_CV_{Si} in *hh*, *hk*, *kh* and *kk* lattice site configurations.

The extracted parameters of the two levels *A* and *B* from DLTS measurements of samples in this study, together with those obtained for comparable defect levels in [5] and [27], are shown in table 3 for comparison. The trap levels (E_T) and capture cross-sections (σ_n) of *A* and A(2) levels, and *B* and RB1 levels, show reasonable agreement (E_T differs by 0.1 eV at most and σ_n agree within an order of magnitude) for comparable conditions (as-grown with Cl-chemistry). This supports an origin related to the same defect types. As for the Ci₄ and Ci₅ levels, on the other hand, they display quite different trap level parameters, and further studies are needed to determine whether their origin is shared with Cl-related defects appearing in as-grown epitaxial layers. Such a comparison must consider the uncertainties inherent in different measurement setups and Arrhenius analysis for defect parameter extraction, possible variations between as-grown and implanted epitaxial layers, and the influence of doping concentration on defect characteristics.

The common factor across all studies shown in table 3 is the presence of chlorine, introduced either during epitaxial growth or through implantation.

The *A* and *B* defect levels (figures 5(c) and (d)) have also been observed in early studies on Cl-based epitaxial growth of 4H-SiC, although without suggesting an origin and detailed analysis of the defects [34]. Accordingly, the defect levels observed in figures 5(c) and (d) are likely related to the involvement of Cl-related defects in the epitaxial layers. It should be noted once more that the epitaxial layers in this study are grown by a Cl-based chemistry and no such peaks are observed in as-grown epitaxial layers using standard growth chemistry without the addition of Cl. Furthermore, theoretical predictions indicate that the $\text{Cl}_\text{C}\text{V}_\text{Si}$ defect in the positive charge state acts as a color center in the telecom-wavelength band, suggesting its role as a radiative recombination center [33]. Consequently, the defect levels observed as the *A* and *B* DLTS peaks could influence the measured MCL, particularly in samples with low $Z_{1/2}$ concentrations.

In a previous study we have demonstrated the role of boron-related deep-level defects in controlling MCL in low doped 4H-SiC n-type epitaxial layers [10]. We have shown that shallow boron can act as a trapping center for minority carriers whereas, D-center, a deep acceptor level related to boron, can act as a radiative recombination center and hence reduce the MCL in as-grown epitaxial layers. For the three samples from Set-II with low doping concentration (C/Si: 1.1, 1.2, and 1.3), 530 nm TRPL analysis revealed that the shallow boron concentration seems to be similar for both of the hydrocarbons' samples (figure 7(a)). On the other hand, the D-center concentration is significantly higher (no absolute value can be extracted from the 530 nm TRPL decay curves and only qualitative comparison is possible) for the samples grown with C_3H_8 as the carbon source (figure 7(b)). Consequently, it can be also concluded that the higher concentration of D-center in C_3H_8 sampled compared to CH_4 samples is playing a role in the reduced MCL for C_3H_8 samples.

Combining this information with the results observed in figures 5(c), (d), and 7(a), (b), and considering the growth parameters of the studied epitaxial layers, it can be suggested that the type of hydrocarbon and the introduced C/Si ratio can impact both the extent of Cl- and boron-related defect levels formation in 4H-SiC epitaxial layers grown with Cl-based chemistry. The emergence of Cl-related defect levels at higher C/Si ratios, together with the different concentration ratios at each C/Si ratio, can be related to the formation of carbon clusters in the gas phase and, consequently, a reduction in the number of active carbon species on the surface to react with SiCl, resulting in the incorporation of Cl in the 4H-SiC lattice. Here, it should be noted that the main silicon species contributing to the growth in Cl-based chemistry are Si and SiCl [35]. On the other hand, an almost similar difference between the concentration of D-center at all C/Si ratios for the two hydrocarbons suggests that the incorporation of D-center, can be related to the different natures of the two hydrocarbons, however, an underlying mechanism is not understood yet.

The formation of carbon clusters in the gas phase during the CVD epitaxial growth of 4H-SiC has been shown to transform single-crystalline epitaxial layers into polycrystalline layers when using C/Si ratios above 1 at higher growth rates [36]. In our case, the epitaxial layers grown at a high C/Si ratio have not yet transformed into polycrystalline ones. However, the formation of the defects labeled *A* and *B* can indicate a sign for the upper limit for C/Si ratio, and beyond this limit, the epitaxial layer may convert into polycrystalline [37].

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, the present study explores the influence of hydrocarbon choice on the properties of 4H-SiC epitaxial layers grown by Cl-based CVD. Systematic variation of the C/Si and N/C ratios, combined with comprehensive characterization, reveals the intricate dependence of material properties on these growth parameters. Specifically, we observe that the choice of hydrocarbon significantly impacts nitrogen doping incorporation, particularly at lower N/C ratios. This disparity is likely linked to differences in the surface diffusivity of the species arising from each hydrocarbon, influencing the site-competition mechanism during nitrogen incorporation at lower doping levels. Furthermore, TRPL studies reveal a notable difference in MCL between the two hydrocarbons, with CH_4 consistently yielding longer MCLs. An order of magnitude lower concentration of $Z_{1/2}$ is observed at low C/Si ratio of 0.9 with CH_4 , however, above C/Si:1 similar $Z_{1/2}$ concentrations was measured for both of the hydrocarbons. Additionally, a C/Si ratio of 1.0 was associated with both the lowest $Z_{1/2}$ concentration, indicative of minimal carbon vacancy formation, and the minimum nitrogen doping concentration, suggesting an optimal condition for gas-phase chemistry and thermodynamic equilibrium, which leads to improved material quality. DLTS analysis indicates the presence of two additional deep-level defects, potentially caused by Cl-related defects, with concentrations varying depending on the hydrocarbon and C/Si ratio. These defects are likely contributing to the observed MCL differences. 530 nm TRPL analysis also revealed the presence of a higher concentration of D-center in C_3H_8 samples, potentially leading to further lower MCL of these samples compared to CH_4 samples. While further investigations are necessary to fully elucidate the roles of different hydrocarbons on the studied parameters,

the present study contributes to the ongoing refinement of growth strategies aiming to achieve precise control over material properties for advanced power electronics and quantum devices.

Data availability statement

The data cannot be made publicly available upon publication because they are not available in a format that is sufficiently accessible or reusable by other researchers. The data that support the findings of this study are available upon reasonable request from the authors.

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Conflict of interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Author contributions

Misagh Ghezellou: Conceptualization (equal); Data curation (lead); Formal analysis (lead); Investigation (lead); Methodology (equal); Validation (lead); Visualization (lead); Writing—original draft (lead). **Erlend Lemva Ousdal:** Formal analysis (supporting); Investigation (supporting); Validation (supporting). **Marianne E Bathen:** Formal analysis (supporting); Investigation (supporting); Validation (supporting); Writing—review & editing (supporting). **Lasse Vines:** Formal analysis (supporting); Resources (supporting); supervision (supporting). **Jawad Ul-Hassan:** Conceptualization (equal); Formal analysis (supporting); Funding acquisition (lead); Methodology (equal); Project administration (lead); Resources (lead); Supervision (lead); Validation (equal); Writing—review & editing (lead)

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